

Influence of Political Parties, Bureaucracy Authority, Role of Election Supervisory Committee and Community Participation on the Performance of General Elections Commission

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Abstract: The community has a very important role in organizing a democratic party such as the Local Leaders Election. The purpose of this research is to improve the performance of general elections commission (KPU) of Ternate city in order to make people trust, and it is the role of government to increase the participation of qualified and responsible society in political life.

This research uses quantitative approach which is explanatory research. Sampling using proportionate stratified random sampling technique with 460 samples and data analysis with simple and multiple linear regression.

The result of the research shows that: (1) Political parties has influence of 49,8% to KPU performance of Ternate City, because political party is a strengthening factor, (2) bureaucracy authority to KPU performance has influence 52,9%, because bureaucratic authority is supporting factor (3) the role of Election Supervisory Committee (Panwaslu) on the performance of Ternate Regency KPU has 72.8% influence, because the role of Panwaslu is the main factor, (4) Public participation on KPU performance of Ternate City has an influence of 54.9%, because community participation is a supporting factor, (5) Political parties, bureaucratic authorities, Role of Election Supervisory Committee, and community participation together have a 78.1% influence on the performance of KPU of Ternate City. It needs a legislation that can be the basis for effective and functional political parties growth.

Keywords: political parties, bureaucracy, panwaslu, community participation and KPU

I. Background

General elections commission (KPU) as the organizer of General Election and as mandated in Law N0. 15/2011 in conducting the General Election is committed and guided by the principle of independence, honest, fair, orderly in conducting General Election, open, professional, efficient and effective considering KPU duty is to organize Indonesian Legislative Election, Local Leaders Election and Presidential Election held directly by the people.

General Elections have meaning and significance as a means of manifesting the sovereignty of the people in order to produce a democratic Indonesian state government, because the characteristic of a democratic country is the existence of elections.

The implementation of the General Elections shall be held once every five years, as set forth in Article 22E Paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution. The General Elections shall be conducted in a direct, public, free, secret, honest and fair manner every five years, Of Law No. 22/2007 regarding the holding of General Elections. General Election which is one form of community involvement in the political process is also a means for the community to participate in determining the figure and direction of state or regional leadership within a certain period. When democracy gets widespread attention from the world community, democratic elections are an essential prerequisite for the establishment of a country's leadership. Elections have a role to produce leadership that is really close to the will of the people and is one of the legitimate means of obtaining legitimacy of power based on the constitution of the law.

From the results of observations in the field found some problems that affect the performance of the KPU:

- 1) Socialization of legislative candidates is still considered not optimal. The reason, in soasialisasi just look at who the candidate, not from the work program that will be done candidates.
- 2) Performance of KPU is considered still not carrying out its responsibility in securing election data.
- 3) There is suspicion of the emergence of illegal voter cards intending to inflame a particular party or candidate vote.
- 4) There is still an activity to distribute money or goods to voters with the aim that voters give their votes to the giver.
- 5) The occurrence of clashes between supporters during the campaign.
- 6) The existence of political violence in the name of primordialism is always successful to obtain votes in some areas.
- 7) People whose economic conditions are difficult and their political knowledge is still common will be the target of perpetrators of money politics practice.
- 8) There is a power lapse such as exploitation of the budget, the capitalization of policies, and the exploitation of existing resources as reciprocity at large costs when the money politician is campaigning.
- 9) Inconsistent decisions / policies and disadvantages of election participants, inaccuracies in vote counting, to any indication of election to any of the election participants.
- 10) Panwaslu does not perform its duties properly in overseeing the holding of General Elections throughout the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

Based on the above, the framework in this study can be described as follows:

Picture 1.1. framework

II. Research methodology

This research used quantitative explanatory research approach that describes the real situation in the field based on facts and existing data that has been verified and tested its truth through a series of statistical tests.

The research variables are classified into five sections, namely independent variables are political parties (X1), bureaucracy authority (X2), role of Panwaslu (X3) and community participation (X4) and dependent variable is performance of KPU (Y). While the technique of data analysis using the formula: (1) Descriptive Statistics (2) Test Validity and Reliability, (3) Classic Assumption Test (Test Data Normality and Multicollinearity), (4) Analyst Determines, (5) Simple Linear Regression Analysis and Hypothesis Testing with t test and F count test. This research was conducted in Ternate City.

The population in this study consists of political parties (Golkar, PAN, PPP, Gerindra and PKS), Bureaucracy (Echelon II, III & IV), Local Leaders Candidates, KPU, Success Team and Community in Ternate City amounted to 731 people, and using the slovin formula obtained a sample of 460 people.

III. Discussion of Research Results

Before the findings of the study are discussed, the following section highlights the results of the tests to examine the data.

Reliability Test

To see the coefficient reliability of the questioners, Alpha Cronbach was calculated by using SPSS, and the results of reliability test for all variables were significant (0,728-0,831). Political parties (X₁) has $\alpha = 0,782$, bureaucracy authority (X₂) has $\alpha = 0,782$, the role of Panwaslu (X₃) has $\alpha = 0,786$ and Community Participation (X₄) has $\alpha = 0,831$ and the dependent variable performance of KPU (Y) has $\alpha = 0,728$. From the results, it can be seen that the questionnaires used for each variable are reliable, because all their coefficient reliability is higher than 0.6.

Validity Test

The validity of each point in the questionnaires was calculated by using "product moment" correlation technique. From 15 questionnaires responded by 460 subjects (n = 460), α value was 0.05. If we compare this value of r-table which is 0,088, it can be concluded that each point in the instrument of all variables were valid (0,211-0,647). Political parties (X₁) has a value of (0,211-0,603), bureaucracy authority (X₂) has a value of (0,282-0,439), the role of Panwaslu (X₃) has a value of (0,305-0,441) and Community Participation (X₄) has a value of (0,211-0,647) and the dependent variable performance of KPU (Y) has a value of (0,224-0,421).

Hypothesis Test

Based on the results of hypothesis testing using the program SPSS 16 for Windows, all show Ho rejected and Ha accepted, and then obtained the regression equation of the fifth hypothesis as follows:

- $\hat{Y}_1 = 1,872 + 0,261X_1$
- $\hat{Y}_2 = 1,939 + 0,395X_2$
- $\hat{Y}_3 = 2,261 + 0,482X_3$
- $\hat{Y}_4 = 2,122 + 0,421X_4$
- $\hat{Y} = 1,897 + 0,093X_1 + 0,081X_2 + 0,094X_3 + 0,082X_4$

1. The Influence of Political Parties on Performance of KPU in Ternate City.

Participation of political parties in giving color during the elections in Ternate City has a positive impact for the implementation of the election of the best leaders of the region. Positive impact is a form of impact that gives the impact of progress, smoothness for the implementation of elections in Ternate City from the role of the political party. Positive implications include:

- 1) The Party has a meaningful role in delivering the daughters of the region in fighting for the leadership seat to the position as head of the region.
- 2) For the voters, in the presence of political party mechanism, the people have been provided by the best candidates for the region as a result of qualification of each political party.

- 3) The party that carries the candidates in the Pilkada also seeks to socialize (introduce) the Local Leaders Candidates through the media campaign to be better known to the public.
- 4) The Party also functions as a regulator of conflict; this is what is able to encourage the creation of a safe and smooth state in the performance process of the Election Commission in Ternate City.
- 5) Political parties are also entitled to oversee the election process up to the final vote counting process, so that various fraud or violations can be suppressed to the maximum extent possible.

The purpose of the formation of political parties is to fight for and defend the political interests of members, society, nation and state, and to maintain the integrity of the Indonesian state.

The statistical results show that political parties contributed significantly 49.8% to the performance of KPU in Ternate City. This means that the better the political party will improve the performance of the KPU.

According to Carl J. Friedrich (2000: 52): Political Parties are a group of people who are organized stably in order to seize or retain government control of their Party leaders, and on the basis of this satisfaction gives members of the Party the ideal and material benefit.

Furthermore Sigmund Neumann (in Budiardjo, 2008: 214) is still about political parties asserting that Political Parties are an articulate organization consisting of active Political actors in the society, those who focus on mastering the power of government and competing for the support of the people and some other groups have different views. Thus, political parties are the great intermediaries that connect social forces and ideologies with official governmental institutions and which relate them to political action within a broader political society.

From the above opinion, political parties are defined as an organized group whose members have the same values and ideals oriented to gain power and seize political sovereignty through the acquired power to carry out their policies.

Opinions and attitudes from various groups that are more or less related to the same thing are combined into a "merger of interests" which in a political system is an input to the government in power. Conversely, if the articulation of opinions and attitudes are not well accumulated then that will arise is a competition of uncontrolled interests and will eventually lead to anarchy. In other words, political parties are in charge of disorderly public will.

2. The Effect of Bureaucracy's Authority on the Performance of KPU in Ternate City.

Governors and Regents/Mayors remain the holders of executive and legislative power, although the implementation of the legislative functions must be done with the approval of the Legislative which is the controlling institution of the power of government in the region.

Government bureaucracy is a government organization run by a command/instruction system consisting of various levels of position (hierarchy) in the form of a pyramid. The largest government bureaucracy in Indonesia is the Republic of Indonesia, led by the president assisted by ministers and heads of state institutions. The ministers and heads of state institutions each lead government bureaucracies within the ministry or state institutions according to the hearing.

The power and authority possessed by officials against the government bureaucracy until now has not been able to realize what the people want. One desired by the people is the presence of a sense of justice. People today often watch television news shows on the number of officials and bureaucracies who are arrested for being involved in corruption issues. The news has shaped the opinion that the government bureaucracy from the past until now has remained unchanged. The bureaucracy does not assist the KPU in carrying out its duties and functions.

The statistical results show that the authority of bureaucracy contributed significantly 52.9% to the performance of General Elections Commission in Ternate City. This means that the better the bureaucratic authority will improve the performance of the KPU.

The understanding of authority according to Budihardjo (2008: 7) is the institutionalized power, the ability to carry out certain legal actions intended to cause legal consequences, and the right which contains the freedom to commit or not to perform certain actions or to demand the other party to perform certain actions.

Sulistiyani (2015:56), Authority Aspect so much influenced by the used Organization structure, especially regulation that needs understanding and knowledge on organization structure to achieve organization goal. With the help of the authority of the bureaucracy, the KPU can improve its performance. Bureaucratic indicators such as remuneration, coercion, legal, control, role model, responsibility, accepting authority, accountability, freedom, decisions, activities, status of office, punishment, information and communication can be used as guidance which must be improved so that KPU can improve its performance.

3. The Effect of Role of Panwaslu on Performance of KPU in Ternate City.

The tasks and authorities of Panwaslu are regulated in Article 77 paragraph (1) Constitution No.15/2011 concerning the Implementation of General Election that is, overseeing the stages of the implementation of General Elections in Regency/Municipality from the initial stage of updating of voter data to the process of determining the results Indonesian Legislative Election, then the stages of receipt of reports or findings of alleged election violations, resolving election violations that have no element of criminal act, submitting recommendation to election organizers who alleged violations of the General Elections to Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu), to submit reports or findings to the competent authorities to resolve them.

The authority of Panwaslu regulated in Article 77 Paragraph (2) of Constitution No.15/2011 concerning the Implementation of General Elections is to provide recommendations to the KPU to temporarily deactivate or impose administrative sanctions on the conduct of elections that violate the General Elections and provide recommendations to the authorities on the findings and reports on reports containing elements of electoral crime.

Panwaslu of Ternate City in tackling criminal acts of General Election through criminal penalty policy consisting of penal effort and non-penal effort. Penalty or repressive efforts focus more on eradication / suppression after a crime which is essentially a part of law enforcement effort.

Then after being reviewed and proven correct, Panwaslu shall follow up the report within 3 (three) days after the report is received. If additional information from the reporting party is still required, the Election Supervisory Committee may extend the period of 5 (five) days from the date of receipt of the report.

Elections are the only democratic procedure that legitimates the powers and actions of representatives of the people to take certain actions. Elections are the mechanism of circulation and regeneration of power. Elections are also the only way to replace the old power without violence (chaos) and coup d'état.

Through elections the people can determine their political stance to keep believing in the old government, or replace it with a new one. In other words, elections are an important means of promoting and seeking accountability from public officials. Through the elections it is expected that the political process that takes place will give birth to a new government that is legitimate, democratic and truly represents the interests of the voting community. Therefore, the ongoing 2009 General Election can no longer be called a democratic experiment that will tolerate the weaknesses and opportunities that can threaten democratic life itself.

The statistic shows that the role of Panwaslu contributed significantly to 72.8% on the performance of Ternate City KPU. This means that the better the role of Panwaslu will improve the performance of the KPU.

According Sarwoto (2001: 95) supervision is the activities of leaders who seek that the work executed in accordance with the plan. The definition of supervision is a follow-up to see whether the planned work has been carried out perfectly and if not, it is necessary to take corrective action in accordance with the applicable provisions. In this research, the supervisor's leadership activities are conducted by Panwaslu.

4. Effect of Public Participation on KPU Performance in Ternate City.

The form of political participation of a visible in his political activities can affect the performance of the KPU. Based on the voters' statements of their community participation, they are:

a. Voting

In connection with the Local Leaders Election (pilkada) in Ternate, the people of Ternate are generally very enthusiastic in giving their voting rights in this election. This matter, seen from news of voting event and vote count which is registered in permanent voter list among others come to TPS to vote or about 78% of Ternate City residents use their voting right in this election.

b. Campaign

Pilkada campaign is a means of democracy party. For the voters as a whole already know the purpose of the campaign and they think that the campaign is an activity to convey information and show the vision, mission and program of political parties in the election so as to attract the sympathizers of the community to vote. The Voter's assumption that's the campaign is a time-consuming activity and must defeat all their daily routines and activities resulted in novice voters being reluctant to participate in campaign activities. Voters assume that campaign activities are a fun activity because they get entertainment and they can also provide support to the legislative candidates they support. But there is also a reason that the pilkada is a mere event rah-rah and the event to gather with friends just do not care about the meaning of the actual campaign activities

c. Speaking of Political Issues

People like to talk about issues and related political events. Although it is informal, it is not uncommon for such discussions to be interesting. Maybe there people are free to express their opinions and political attitude. This is possible because of the friendship and kinship between the participants.

d. As Management of Political Parties

The involvement of voters to participate in the management of political parties has not been so participatory; this is because the voters have not responded very much to the invitation of the party cadres to join the political party membership structure. The proofs of the various parties that exist in only one party that there is a beginner voter join the party. The lack of interest in newbie voters to join in party structures is caused by many factors such as the daily busyness factor so that early voters are difficult to spend time between working with managing political parties.

The form of participation of one's society will be seen in its political activities. The most common form of political participation is voting, either to vote for a candidate or a regional head.

Voters, as an integral part of society, also have an important share in the success of direct elections. The forms of political participation undertaken by the electorate are no different from other people's political activities.

Pilkada is a series of democratic parties of Indonesian society which will then be continued with the presidential and vice presidential elections. It is therefore not surprising that people are so enthusiastic about the success of the show.

This can be proved based on interviews with respondents indicating that all respondents interviewed by the researcher used their voting right in the election. They do so for a variety of reasons, including political awareness because they feel that it is a duty. Besides that is the easiness factor in doing this political activity.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion of Michel Rush and Philip Althoff which states that the most common form of political participation is the voting. Voting is a form of political participation that does not require much effort. This activity is done when needed. To do this activity required only a small initiative (Maran, 2001: 151).

If related to the opinion of Roth and Wilson (Suryadi, 2007: 137), then this form of political participation also lies at the bottom. Such a pyramid with the majority of political participation lies below. This means that the intensity of political participation of most citizens is at the level of the observer. Those belonging to this group usually engage in political activities such as: attending rallies, becoming party members/interest groups, discussing political issues, following political developments through mass media, and voting in local elections.

As a wise society we must participate in the general elections process in order to determine the leader who will lead us. Thus, we will indirectly determine policy makers who will seek to prosper society in general. In participating in the electoral process as an intelligent community we must be able to assess the best candidates who are capable and willing to listen to the aspirations of the community so that development will be done in accordance with the wishes of the community and not choose candidates who are only selfish or group just so forget the promise -a promise already spoken during the campaign period. As the owner of voter rights in the election we should not squander the voting rights just for the temporary lure that in the sense we must cast our vote to the right candidate.

The statistical results show that the participation of the community contributed significantly 54.9% to the performance of Ternate City KPU. This means that the better the community participation will improve the performance of the KPU.

The participation of citizens or citizens in a political activity is inseparable from the political participation of the community. Where's the community, is the most important factor in determining the leaders of government both at the central level to the lowest level of the village. "Participation is the determination of attitudes and the involvement of each individual's desire in the situation and condition of his organization, so that ultimately the individual is to participate in the achievement of organizational goals, and take part in every joint responsibility" (Syafiie, 2002: 132).

Based on the above opinion, then participation is the most important factor in every attitude done by a person or individual both within an organization, which in turn can encourage a person to achieve goals to be achieved by the organization and have joint responsibility of each goal. In addition Ramlan Surbakti also provides the definition of political participation as "Participation is one of the important aspects of democracy. The underlying assumption of democracy (and participation) of the person who knows best about what is good for him is that person. Because political decisions made and implemented by the government concerning and affecting the lives of citizens, the citizens are entitled to participate in determining the content of political decisions "(Surbakti, 1999: 140). Sulistyani (2016:46), by involving the locals, it will helps during the implementation process of the policy since it's based on their needs, with that practice will also encourage people to be more participative in the locals development. It can be said that participation is one of the most important aspects in the implementation of democracy that has an important role. The implementation of democracy can determine political decisions whether it is policy, regulation and others. If there is a policy that does not take sides / harms the community, the public has the right to give opinions/protests in the form of protests because what will be made and implemented government will affect people's lives.

5. The influence of political parties, bureaucratic authority, the role of Panwaslu and community participation together on the performance of KPU in Ternate City.

The performance of KPU in Ternate City in question is the result of work achieved by KPU of Ternate City when conducting verification of candidate member of legislative. Performance in question is the level of conformity programs that have been determined previously by Ternate City KPU.

Achievement of results of verification activities conducted KPU of Ternate City to find out and assess the performance of KPU in conducting verification of candidates for Legislative members. Settlement to assess the performance is inseparable from the process of completion of the performance of KPU itself. With the existence of these indicators, the performance of KPU in verifying the candidates for legislative members can run optimally.

The results of a performance are very important to know in the implementation of an organization, because it can serve as the basis of the determinant of the success of the goal to be achieved. The indicators used in research on the performance of KPU in verifying legislative candidates consist of productivity, service quality, service quality responsiveness, responsibilities, and accountability.

The statistical results show that political parties, bureaucratic authority, role of Panwaslu and community participation contributed significantly to 78.1% on the performance of General Election Commission in Ternate City. That is, the better the political parties, bureaucratic authority, the role of Panwaslu and community participation will improve the performance of KPU. With indicators of its performance is preparing a person, improving conditions, assigning tasks, basics, comparators, determinants, successes, loyalties, crafts, abilities, development, relationships, organizing tasks, accountability and feedback.

Findings of Research Results

1. The Influence of Political Parties on the Performance of KPU

From the results of research can be known to improve performance of KPU in Ternate city can be done by encouraging Political Parties to do:

- Recruitment is done through a multilevel selection procedure from system selection, political party selection, administrative selection, administrative law enforcement selection and political selection;
- Recruitment of the Head of Region as a means of political recruitment is conducted by political mechanism;
- Political parties recruit, educate, and supervise competent staff for their public offices and to occupy seats in parliament.

From the result of the research, it is found that to improve the performance of KPU in Ternate City, the participation of citizens in the political process does not only mean that citizens support the decisions or policies that have been outlined by the leaders, because if this happens then the right term is political mobilization. Political participation is the involvement of citizens at all stages of the policy, from the time of decision-making to judgment of the decision, as well as the opportunity to participate in the execution of the decision. Currently the use of the word participation (politics) more often refers to the support that citizens provide for the execution of decisions already made by political and government leaders. On the contrary we rarely hear the phrase that puts citizens as the main actors of decision-making.

2. The Effect of Bureaucracy's Authority on Performance of KPU

From the research results can be known to improve the performance of KPU in Ternate city can be done by making the Bureaucracy Authority apply:

- Responsibility is the obligation to do something that arises when the KPU accepts the duties of its superiors;
- Receiving authority from the boss is a work to be done;
- In exercising the authority is given freedom in determining the decisions to be taken.

In performing its duties, the KPU and Bawaslu are supported by the Secretariat General to provide administrative technical support. Thus, the main tasks of election organizers are run by the commissioners, while administrative technical support by the secretariat. The advantages of the above institutional pattern are that there is a clear separation of which job is the task of the commissioner and which job is the secretarial task.

The quality of human resources (HR) in general election organizers is good because to enter into the electoral apparatus (both the leadership and secretarial elements) is done through a strict recruitment pattern. However, there are some notes that need attention for improvement, maintaining the continuity and intensity of education and training of election organizers and secretarial units.

3. Influence of Role Panwaslu on Performance of KPU

From the results of the study found that to improve the performance of KPU in Ternate City, Panwaslu must implement:

- Organizational solidity, quality of human resources and effective and efficient management of election supervisory institutions;
- Establish a system of surveillance capable of rapid detection and early prevention of potential violations in a concrete, measurable, and systematic manner;
- Provide a national control system in a structured, systematic, and integrative supervision management based on technology;
- Improve the quality of election violation handling performance professionally, with the principle of simple, cheap, and accountable;
- Establish an effective and efficient election dispute resolution system so as to make consistent and fair judgments;

4. Effect of Public Participation on Performance of KPU

From the results of the research can be known to improve the performance of KPU in Ternate city can be done by increasing Community Participation, must implemented:

- All state institutions and the wider community are encouraged to enforce national laws and local regulations effectively.
- The community conducts monitoring and evaluation of activities.
- Utilization of results of community empowerment program activities for the general welfare of the community.

Practical Implications

KPU is the front guard in a country. Moreover, in organizing the election, KPU is not only dealing with political parties participating in the election, but also must deal directly with the government and the wider community. Under these conditions, KPUs are often in a dilemmatic position. On the one hand, the KPU seeks to serve and fulfill the interests of all parties (political parties, government and society). On the other hand, the KPU must be consistent in implementing all applicable legislation in which the interests of the parties are limited. Purpose and Objectives of the preparation of Performance Accountability Report of Government Institution (LAKIP) KPU is as a form of KPU responsibility for the implementation of its duties and functions, and as an analysis material in making policy to improve the performance in the future.

- 1) Plan the program and budget and set a schedule;
- 2) Compile and define working procedures of KPU;
- 3) Develop and establish technical guidelines for each stage of the General Elections after consultation with Parliament and Government first;
- 4) Coordinate, organize, and control all stages of the General Election;

IV. Conclusion

1. The magnitude of Political Parties influence on Performance of KPU in Ternate City is 49.8%. This shows the importance of Political Parties to the Performance of KPU in Ternate City, related to political communication, political socialization, political recruitment, conflict regulator, recruitment of head of region, people selection, political map, registration period, selection of candidates, selection procedure, platform, offer policy alternatives, recruit staff and socialize members.
2. The magnitude of the influence of Bureaucratic Authority on the Performance of KPU in Ternate City is 52.9%. This indicates the importance of Bureaucracy Authority on the Performance of KPU in Ternate City, related to compensation, coercion, legal, control, role model, responsibility, accepting authority, accountability, freedom, decision, activity, position status, punish, information and communication.
3. The magnitude of the influence Role of Panwaslu on Performance of KPU in Ternate City is 72.8%. This indicates the importance of the role of Panwaslu to the Performance of KPU in Ternate City, related to action, prevention, refinement, improvement, feedback, good relations, friendly and obedient, success, management effectiveness, assurance, physical exertion, mind, way of working, responsibility.
4. There is a large influence of Community Participation on the Performance of KPU in Ternate City by 54.9%. This indicates the importance of Public Participation to Performance of KPU in Ternate City, related to horizontal, vertical, relationship, manner, decision making, security and order, political, economic, social, culture, decision making, activity planning, activity implementation, monitoring and evaluation activities and utilization of activity results.
5. The magnitude of the influence of Political Parties, Bureaucracy Authority, the Role of Panwaslu and the Community Participation collectively to the Performance of KPU in Ternate City amounted to 78.1%. In this case, the main factor affecting Performance of KPU is the Role of Panwaslu variable with the value of 0.464 units, the supporting factor is the Community Participation variable with the value of 0.340 units and the Bureaucracy Authority with the value of 0.283 units, the reinforcing factor is the Political Party variable with the value of 0.236 units, someone, improving conditions, assigning tasks, basics, comparators, determinants, successes, loyalties, crafts, abilities, development, relationships, carrying out tasks, accountability and feedback.

V Suggestions

1. Political Parties needs to conduct initial selection to the community about what kind of figure is coveted to become head of region.
2. It is necessary to establish a common view among direct election participants that direct Pilkada is a method, procedure or a way to achieve the quality and substance of democracy, with the ultimate goal for the formation of trusted regional leadership.
3. To improve the performance of the Panwaslu, there needs to be maximum cooperation and supervision from all levels of Panwaslu, and the need for increased training or simulation from the initial stage of the selection of permanent voters list to the final stages of recapitulation and determination of results voice in this case to will support good cooperation and maximum result for all Panwaslu, both city Panwaslu and Sub-district Panwaslu for supervision of general election of President and Vice President can be done well.
4. To succeed KPU activities in the future, the KPU recommends to the Provincial KPU, Regency/City KPU to prepare Performance Accountability Report of Government Agencies (LAKIP) KPU in accordance with the condition of each region. All

performance indicators and activities undertaken by KPU through Media Center KPU and vice versa all activities that have been done to KPU so that communication with all KPU in the country can increasing the performance of KPU.

5. The role of political parties has contributed significantly to the national political system, especially in the dynamic and changing lives of the Indonesian people. If the capacity and performance of political parties can be improved, this will have a major impact on improving the quality of democracy and the performance of the political system. The role of political parties should be enhanced their capacity, quality and performance in order to realize the aspirations and wishes of the people and improve the quality of democracy.

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